

A STUDY ON RISK MANAGEMENT IN CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS - AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

V. Sankara Subramaniyan* & K. Veerakumar**

* Vice Principal & Professor of Civil Engineering, Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur, Tamilnadu

** Assistant Professor in Commerce - BPS, NGM College (Autonomous), Pollachi, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: V. Sankara Subramaniyan & K. Veerakumar, "A Study on Risk Management in Construction Projects - An Empirical Study", International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology, Page Number 1-4, Volume 2, Issue 1, 2017

Abstract:

There are lots of risks in constructional projects. Risks can come from various sources including uncertainty in financial markets, threats from project failures, legal liabilities, credit risk, accidents, natural causes and disasters, deliberate attack from an adversary, or events of uncertain or unpredictable root-cause. In this paper, an attempt has been made to find the risk management in constructional projects. Samples of 100 respondents were randomly selected from Salem District. It is found that two variables namely monthly income, occupation have been correlated with the respondents risk in construction projects.

Key Words: Risk, Construction, Projects, Finance, Legal & Environment

Introduction:

Risks can come from various sources including uncertainty in financial markets, threats from project failures, legal liabilities, credit risk, accidents, natural causes and disasters, deliberate attack from an adversary, or events of uncertain or unpredictable root-cause. There are two types of events. They are

- ✓ Negative events can be classified as risks
- ✓ Positive events are classified as opportunities.

Construction projects are very complex projects, where uncertainty comes from various sources. Risk management plays an important role in construction project. Risk management is the identification, assessment, and prioritization of risks followed by coordinated and economical application of resources

- ✓ To minimize, monitor, and control the probability
- ✓ To impact of unfortunate event
- ✓ To maximize the realization of opportunities
- ✓ To assure uncertainty does not deflect the endeavor from the business goals.

Types of Risk:

Pure and Particular Risk: It includes damage to persons and property (such as fire, storm, water, collapse, subsidence, vibration, etc.) Contract conditions often make it a contractual obligation to take out insurance cover against these risks.

Fundamental Risk: It includes external factors such as: damage due to war, nuclear pollution and supersonic bangs; government policy on taxes, labour, safety or other laws; malicious damage; and industrial disputes. Such incidents are all the subject of statutory liability and no insurance cover is normally available or needed.

Speculative Risk: It is something which can be apportioned in advance as decided by the parties to the contract. This may include losses in time and money, which result from unexpected ground conditions, exceptionally adverse weather, unforeseeable shortages of labour or materials, and other similar matters beyond the control of the contractor.

There are also risks of losses of time and money, poor direction, supervision or communication; delays in payment; and delay in resolving disputes. Risk management includes risks that may happen in the construction environment. According to the construction project one cannot make the project totally risk free but ensure that precautionary steps are taken to meet those. It expects the individuals to be reasonably practical. The following are the five steps to handle risk:

- Step 1: Identify the hazards
- Step 2: Regarding the individuals who may be harmed
- Step 3: Assess the risks and settle on safety measures
- Step 4: Document result and apply them
- Step 5: Evaluation of risk assessment and revise if essential

Review of Literature:

A. Suchith Reddy (2010) investigated to acquire an overall idea about risk and its consequences in construction field and the process required for its management. The objective of the research is to explore the effective way for implementation of risk management in construction industry. The researcher have conducted a survey on the following aspects of it, a) Identify, characterize, and assess threats involved in the construction industry b) Assess the vulnerability of critical assets to specific threats. c) Determine the risk d) identifies ways to reduce those risks. e) Prioritize risk reduction measures based on a strategy.

Dr. M. J. Kolhatkar and Amit Bijon Dutta (2013) stated that in order to achieve the project objectives in terms of time, cost, quality, safety and environmental sustainability. The researcher argues that the Risk is the Possibility of suffering loss and the impact on the involved parties. Risk is identified and then risk assessment and analysis is done. Then risk management and risk mitigation is carried out. Risk affect construction sector negatively and focusing on risk reduction measure it important. The main objective of this study is to study different types of risk, factors affecting risk, common sources of risk, advantage and disadvantage of risk management in construction projects.

Satish K. Kamane, Sandip A. Mahadik revealed that construction projects gather together hundreds of stakeholders, which makes it difficult to study a network as a whole and also these projects offer an ideal environment for network and risk management research. Additionally, construction projects are frequently used in management research, and several different tools and techniques have already been developed and especially for this type of project. The researcher find that there is a gap between risk management techniques and their practical application by construction contractor. This research also identify the risk by different methods, types of risks associated with construction project and different risk mitigation techniques.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To describe the risk management in construction project.
- ✓ To analyze the demographic profile of the respondents in Salem District.
- ✓ To identify the level of risk in construction projects.

Research Methodology:

Area of the Study: The research study was done in Salem District.

Sample Design: This is both descriptive and analytical research in nature. These respondents were conveniently selected in Salem District.

Nature and Source of Data: The data needed for the study is both primary and secondary data. Primary data is collected through survey method and secondary data collected through journals, books, internet, etc.,

Sample Size: A total of 100 respondents in Salem District are taken as sample.

Statistical Tools Used for the Study: The collected information were reviewed and consolidated into a master table. For the purpose of analysis the data were further processed by using statistical tools. The statistical tools are

- ✓ Simple Percentage
- ✓ Correlation
- ✓ Friedman Ranking Test

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The study is restricted to the selected sample of Salem District and hence the result of the study cannot be generalized.
- ✓ The statistical methods used to analyze the data have their own limitation.
- ✓ All the limitations of primary data are applicable to this study.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Demographic Profile of the People:

Table 1 describes the demographic profile of the respondents for the study. Out of 100 respondents who were taken for the study: it has been identified that most (53%) of the respondent are male, (47%) whose age group is under 26 to 50 years, most (58%) of the respondents are up to school level, (57%) of the respondents are employee, the annual income of (49%) respondents is Rs.1,00,000 , (54%) of the respondents belong to nuclear family and (59%) of the respondents are married.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Factors	Number of Respondents N=100	Percentage
Gender		
Male	53	53
Female	47	47
Age (Years)		
Up to 25	24	24
26 to 50	47	47
Above 50	29	29
Educational Qualification		
Up to School Level	58	58
Graduate	31	31
Professionals	11	11
Occupation		
Employee	57	57

Officer	35	35
Professionals	08	08
Annual Income		
Up to Rs.1,00,000	49	49
Rs.1,00,001 to Rs.2,50,000	38	38
Above Rs.2,50,000	13	13
Type of Family		
Nuclear Family	46	46
Joint Family	54	54
Marital Status		
Married	59	59
Unmarried	41	41

Table 2: Risk Factors Associated With Respondents - Correlation Analysis

Factors	R	r ²
Gender	0.019	0
Age	0.022	0
Educational Qualification	0.038	0.001
Occupation	0.061*	0.02
Monthly Income	0.199**	0.04
Nature of Family	0.049	0.002
Marital Status	0.003	0

* Significant at five per cent level

** Significant at one per cent level

Occupation: Correlation analysis indicates that these two variables are positively correlated indicating that level of risk is more with respondents who are employees. The coefficient of determination (r^2) shows that occupation accounts for 2 per cent of the variation in the level of risk at five percent level of significance.

Monthly Income: The correlation analysis shows that these two variables are positively correlated indicating that as the monthly income increases the level of risk of the respondents also increases. The coefficient of determination (r^2) shows that monthly income of the respondents account for 4 percent of variations in the level of risk at one percent level of significance.

Table 3: Risk Faced by Respondent in Construction Projects – Friedman Rank Test

Risk	SA	A	NANDA	DA	SDA	Total	Average Rank	Rank
Financial Risk	106	180	99	48	4	437	6.39	1
	(24.26)	(41.19)	(22.65)	(10.98)	(0.92)	(100.00)		
Political Risk	64	137	192	41	3	437	5.57	3
	(14.65)	(31.35)	(43.94)	(9.38)	(0.69)	(100.00)		
Legal Risk	51	154	169	60	3	437	5.32	5
	(11.67)	(35.24)	(38.67)	(13.73)	(0.69)	(100.00)		
Operating Risk	70	125	202	35	5	437	5.61	2
	(16.02)	(28.60)	(46.22)	(8.01)	(1.14)	(100.00)		
Environmental Risk	63	155	152	55	12	437	5.54	4
	(14.42)	(35.47)	(34.78)	(12.59)	(2.75)	(100.00)		

The above table shows about the Friedman Rank Test for risk faced by respondents in construction project were the level of significance is at 0.000 which shows that there is a relationship between the ranks given. From the Friedman Ranking Test, it is found that respondents have financial risk, operating risk, political risk, environment risk and legal risk. Majority of the respondents feel that there is a financial risk in construction projects.

Conclusions:

Construction industry plays an important role in growth of the economy. The risk is very high in construction business. In construction management, risk of the project should be closely monitored. Hence proper risk management is necessary in every step of the activity. It should be properly managed through well trained, qualified and experienced personnel. So that only construction project can achieve its goal apart from many physical, financial and social hazards.

References:

1. Anna Klemetti” Risk Management in Construction Project Network” Laboratory of Industrial Management Report 2006
2. Bayu Aditya, Bambang” Risk Analysis in Feasibility Study of Building Construction Project” The Tenth East Asia-Pacific Conference on Structural Engineering and Construction, August 3-5, 2006, Bangkok, Thailand

3. Building Future Planning “Risk Assessment Planning”2000
4. Debasis Sarkar,Gautam Data” A Framework Of Project Risk Management For The Underground Corridor Construction Of Metro Rail” W.P. No. 2011-02-05.
5. Dr. M. J. Kolhatkar and Er. Amit Bijon Dutta, Study of Risk in Construction Projects Global Research Analysis, Vol.2, Issue 9, 2013
6. Mr. Satish K. Kamane, Mr. Sandip A. Mahadik, Risk Management in Construction Industry IOSR Journal of Mechanical and Civil Engineering (IOSR-JMCE) Issn: 2278-1684, Pp: 59-65
7. A. Suchith Reddy (2010), Risk Management in Construction Industry -A Case Study, International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology, Vol. 4, Issue 10, October 2015
8. K. Veerakumar, “A Study on People Impact on Demonetization”, International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 2, Issue 1, Page Number 9-12, 2017
9. Yang J, Shen Gq, Ho M, Drew Ds, Chan Apc. Exploring Critical Success Factors for Stakeholder Management in Construction Projects. J Civil Eng Manage 2009; 15(4):337– 348.
10. Zavadskas EK, Kaklauskas A, Banaitiene N. Multiple Criteria Analysis of a Building Lifecycle. Vilnius: Technika; 2001. (In Lithuanian)
11. P. Senthilkumar, “A Study on Investment Pattern and Awareness of Farmers in Pollachi Thaluk”, International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 2, Issue 1, Page Number 4-8, 2017
12. V. Sureshkumar, “Impact of Agricultural Schemes by Central Government – A Status Study on Farmers of Pollachi, Coimbatore District, Tamilnadu”, International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 2, Issue 1, Page Number 21-28, 2017
13. Dr. A. John Ditto, “A Study on Customer Perception and Satisfaction towards Net Banking”, International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 2, Issue 1, Page Number 29-32, 2017
14. Dr. K. Sathyaprasad & Dr. I. Siddiq, “Awareness of Rural Consumer on Branded Health Food Drinks”, International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education, Volume 2, Issue 1, Page Number 1-7, 2017.
15. Dr. V. Seetha & J. Suganya, “A Study on Impulsive Consumer Behaviour and Its Determinants”, International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education, Volume 2, Issue 1, Page Number 12-17, 2017.
16. Dr. K. Ramamurthi & A. Arun, “Factors Influencing Buying Behaviour of Rural and Urban Consumers of Select Personal Hygiene Products in Coimbatore Region, Tamilnadu”, International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 11-17, 2017.
17. N. Jisha & Dr. C. R. Karpagam, “A Study on Level of Satisfaction of Customers Towards Various Technology Used in Public Sector Banks With Reference to Coimbatore District”, International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 18-22, 2017.